

Correlation analysis of factors influencing customer loyalty in retail pharmacy chains: A cross-sectional study in Vietnam

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Abstract

The retail pharmacy sector has been a growing market in Vietnam in recent years, leading to a rise in pharmacies in residential areas. This study aims to analyze factors affecting customer loyalty to retail pharmacy chains in Can Tho city. The data was collected through interviews with 747 customers who purchased medication from pharmacy chains via a pre-designed research questionnaire. Four of 32 variables were eliminated after Cronbach's alpha was run. KMO coefficient (0.886–0.91), total variance extracted (> 50%), and Eigenvalue coefficients were all greater than 1 ($p < 0.05$). CFA and SEM results were consistent with market data. Pharmacy chain brands, price, facilities, convenience, employee knowledge, and selling skills had positively influenced loyalty ($p < 0.05$). Pharmacies should apply competitive strategies that prioritize valued services, adapt to customer expectations, and build loyal clientele for a distinct market advantage.

Keywords

influencing factors, loyalty, retail pharmacy chain, satisfaction, Can Tho City

Introduction

Across various industries, studies have demonstrated that significant value is created when companies build loyalty with their customers, employees, and shareholders (Shamsudin et al. 2015). Trust, commitment, and satisfaction have a significant and positive influence on

customers' loyalty attitudes. Additionally, these attitudes have been found to impact actual customers' loyalty behaviors positively and significantly (Ledikwe et al. 2019). In recent years, patients have shown a growing interest in the quality of health services. While ensuring accessibility was once the primary focus in meeting patient demands, the increased supply has expanded patient options (Chang

et al. 2017). In the pharmaceutical industry, customer loyalty is essential for pharmacy chains to attract and retain customers. Currently, due to economic challenges and prolonged hospital treatment times, more and more people with non-critical illnesses visit local pharmacies for consultation. Retail pharmacies and pharmacy chains play an important role in the pharmaceutical industry, supplying medications to individuals. Loyalty is defined as “the degree to which a customer exhibits repurchasing behavior from a service provider, possesses a positive attitudinal disposition toward the provider, and considers using only this provider’s services when a need for this service arises” (Nikolova et al. 2017).

The Vietnamese pharmaceutical market has shown steady growth in recent years, with a compound annual growth rate of approximately 10%. Vietnam’s pharmaceutical market is projected to grow steadily at an annual rate of 4.25% between 2024 and 2029, reaching an estimated US\$2.96 billion by the latter year (Statista 2024). This increasing demand, coupled with advancements in healthcare, makes the strategy of high-tech pharmaceutical production by Vietnamese enterprises crucial for ensuring domestic drug availability and enabling their entry into the global supply chain. The demand for pharmaceuticals is increasing rapidly due to high economic growth, rising per capita income, and heightened awareness of health issues among the population. As a result, many retail pharmacies and pharmacy chains, such as Long Chau, Pharmacy, and others, began to expand dramatically. However, customer loyalty becomes more difficult to obtain as drugstore chains employ increasingly distinctive techniques to adapt to the ever-changing nature of the pharmaceutical market (Gakuya and Mbugua 2018). Retaining loyal customers is challenging when competitors are implementing customer attraction strategies to increase their market share. If pharmacy chains cannot meet customer needs or provide poor services, they will struggle to succeed in a crowded market.

In fact, there have been few studies on customer loyalty to pharmacy chains in the Mekong Delta. Therefore, our study was conducted to help pharmacy chains understand the factors that contribute to client retention and improve service quality. The purpose of our research is to identify the factors affecting customer loyalty to pharmacy chains in Can Tho City.

Materials and methods

Research subjects

Individuals who purchased medicines at chain pharmacies located in nine districts of Can Tho City.

Selection criteria

Customers who have bought drugs at least once from pharmacies of pharmaceutical retail chains. Respondents must have practical experience with and an interest in the chain’s products and services (Moreira and Silva 2015).

Exclusion criteria

Exclude responses that are incomplete, invalid, left blank, or not filled in proper sequence. Also exclude respondents who have not actively sought information in recent years.

Theoretical foundation

We selected the “theory of planned behavior (TPB)” as our theoretical foundation. This theory, founded and developed by social psychologist Ajzen, holds significance in the field of mentality and behavioral science” (Ajzen 1991). TPB is widely used in research aimed at predicting and explaining human behaviors (Zhang and Zhou 2019). Besides subjective norms and behavioral control, another factor that can influence patient loyalty is trust. The relationship marketing literature has revealed that trust is a key factor in building customer loyalty (Larsson and Wilde Larsson 2010; Vinagre and Neves 2010) (Fig. 1).

Hypothesis: Product quality, brand name, price, facilities, convenience, advertising, knowledge of employees, and salesmanship have a positive impact on customer loyalty toward pharmacy chains in Can Tho City.

Design survey questionnaires and measurement scales

This study utilized a cross-sectional descriptive research design and collected data through direct phone interviews, Google Forms, or printed questionnaires with clients who purchased drugs at pharmacy chains or hospitals in Can Tho City. The interviews were conducted using a

Figure 1. Research model.

set of questions to evaluate loyalty and factors influencing clients' decisions to return to the pharmacy chain for future purchases. The survey questionnaire is designed based on outcome-oriented questions. Some previous studies included additional clarifying questions such as, does subjective norm affect customer loyalty? Does perceived behavioral control affect customer loyalty? Does trust affect customer loyalty? Or identify some key factors that make the difference between service quality and satisfaction (Vinagre and Neves 2010; Abrahamsen Grøndahl et al. 2013; Sumaedi et al. 2015).

The first part of the questionnaire is a closed-ended type, where most questions require respondents to choose from predefined options, typically using checkboxes (✓). It focuses on collecting demographic information such as full name, gender, year of birth, area of residence, occupation, and income level. Some questions permit limited open-ended responses; for instance, the income question includes an "Other (please specify)" option, which gives participants room to elaborate if the provided choices are not applicable. This structured design allows for standardized data collection, making analysis and interpretation more efficient. To ensure validity, responses should be checked for completeness, consistency, and relevance (e.g., avoiding blank fields or conflicting answers). Clear instructions and proper quality control during data collection can help improve the reliability of the survey results and identify statistically significant factors that have an impact on the scale/dependent variable. Respondents were required to fill in the available spaces with their information.

The second part involves assessing a combination of factors affecting customer loyalty in chain systems. These factors include product quality (3 items), pharmacy chain brand (3 items), price (3 items), facilities (3 items), convenience (3 items), promotional programs (3 items), along with the professional knowledge of the staff (3 items), and salesmanship (4 items) (Grøndahl et al. 2011). To evaluate these factors, a relatively popular measurement scale in scientific research questionnaires was used to verify individual opinions, behaviors, and perceptions. This section of the questionnaire uses a Likert scale-based instrument designed to measure respondents' level of agreement with specific statements related to product quality and brand trust. Each item provides five response options: 1 = "strongly disagree," 2 = "disagree," 3 = "neutral," 4 = "agree," and 5 = "completely agree" (Kondasani and Panda 2015). This format supports the validation of customer experience by providing consistent response categories, and it enables researchers to measure sentiment or satisfaction levels in a standardized way.

The scale achieved reliability with a Cronbach's alpha (CA) coefficient of ≥ 0.6 and a total variable correlation coefficient of > 0.3 (Carpenter 2018).

In exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the criteria for sample size appropriateness include a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient ranging from 0.5 to 1, a significant Bartlett test ($p < 0.05$), and a factor loading of at least 0.3 (Taherdoost et al. 2022). A loading factor of 0.5 indicates

good statistical significance, with a total extracted variance $\geq 50\%$. Eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) assesses the fit of a measurement model to actual data, enhancing reliability and validity and refining model suitability (Mishra 2016). CFA is a powerful statistical technique used to assess the fit between a previously constructed theoretical model (including latent factors) and the actual data collected. In a research context, CFA plays a key role in validating the structure of a scale. The main purpose of CFA is to confirm the validity of the scale, ensuring that the indicators used truly represent theoretical factors such as product quality, price, and sales skills, thereby forming broader concepts such as "loyalty." The results of CFA analysis are evaluated through fit indices such as CFI, TLI, RMSEA, and GFI.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a second-generation statistical technique used to analyze multidimensional relationships between variables. It visually represents these relationships and enhances theoretical predictions by specifying measurement properties and the relationships between latent variables (Haenlein and Kaplan 2004; Brown and Moore 2012). SEM allows researchers to simultaneously test complex causal relationships between multiple variables, including latent variables. In research, SEM is applied to test and quantify the impact of factors such as price, product quality, brand reputation, etc. on target variables such as customer loyalty. The significance of the results of SEM analysis is expressed in the statistical significance of the relationships (usually assessed by the p-value, with a common threshold of $p < 0.05$) and the sign of the regression coefficient.

Sample size

To conduct EFA, a large sample size is required and is determined based on the minimum sample size and the number of variables included in the analysis. With a minimum observation/variable ratio of 5:1 and 32 questions in the adjusted survey, the calculated minimum sample size was 160 (Carpenter 2018). In this study, the actual sample size was 747, meeting the sample size requirements.

Survey methods

Convenient random sampling was employed using survey methods through direct phone interviews, Google Forms, or printed questionnaires with customers who purchased medicines at pharmacy chains or met the sampling criteria in Can Tho City during the 2023–2024 period. Participants completed surveys based on their real-life experiences purchasing and using services at these chains (Huang et al. 2021).

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0, using descriptive statistical data analysis to calculate frequency, mean, and standard deviation. Correlation analysis was also performed to assess the degree of correlation between

variables. Finally, AMOS software was used for moderation-mediation analysis, which included regression calculations, CFA, and SEM (Stepurko et al. 2016; Van Fleet and Peterson 2016; Zhou et al. 2017).

Abbreviations

PQ	Product quality
BN	Brand name
P	Price
F	Facilities
C	Convenience
ACP	Advertising and consumer promotion
SS	Selling skills
L	Loyalty
CA	Cronbach's alpha
TLI	Tucker-Lewis index
CFI	Comparative fit index
GFI	Goodness of Fit index
RMSEA	Root mean square error approximation
PCLOSE	Probability of close fit

Results

General characteristics of the study sample

Table 1 shows that most study subjects are female (62.2%), while male customers make up a smaller proportion (37.8%). Notably, a high proportion of respondents (80.7%) indicated that pharmacy chains are their first choice for medical needs.

Cronbach's alpha testing results

As shown in Table 2, several factors were eliminated due to their impact on the CA coefficient. Factors P2, C2, ACP3, and L4 were removed because the CA coefficient increased after their removal ($0.991 > 0.989$; $0.999 > 0.983$; $0.966 > 0.963$; $0.977 > 0.975$). In contrast, the remaining factors were retained because they met the required conditions.

Cronbach's alpha values for CSR, trust, and customer loyalty (including loyalty and common behavior) are presented in Table 3.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

The extracted variance value surpassed 70%, reaching 93.839%. Simultaneously, KMO = 0.886 ($0.5 \leq \text{KMO} \leq 1$) and Bartlett's test with sig. = 0.000. The six groups of factors extracted at Eigenvalue = 1.014 (>1) all meet the conditions (Table 4). During the rotated exploratory factor analysis (EFA), a new factor emerged, consisting of items from multiple original subsections (SS1, SS3, SS4, SS2, KE1, KE2, KE3, C1, and C3). This factor was not labeled due to its mixed composition. Meanwhile, the remaining factors reorganized items from their original subsections

into corresponding new constructs, and these factors were not renamed. Therefore, the variables retained after EFA analysis fully satisfy the condition that the loading factor is greater than 0.5, indicating their significant role and practical meaning.

Table 5 indicates that the analysis results show satisfaction with a KMO value = 0.910, Bartlett's test with sig. = 0.000, and an Eigenvalue = 5.385 (>1), meaning that one factor was extracted. The total variance extracted was 89.742% ($>50\%$). As a result, EFA analysis was conducted with the observed variables of the dependent component "(L): Loyalty.

Results of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)

According to Fig. 2, the model appears to be a good fit for the actual data, with the following good fit indices: TLI = 0.975, CFI = 0.981, GFI = 0.916 (>0.9), RMSEA = 0.057 (<0.08), PCLOSE = 0.002, and Chi-square/df = 3.414 (<5). All standardized factor loadings met the criteria, indicating that each observed variable significantly

Table 1. The general characteristics of research subjects.

Sample characteristics	Frequency (n = 747)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	282	37.8
Female	465	62.2
Career		
Agriculture	40	5.4
Sales executive	72	9.6
Public servant	89	11.9
Office employee	33	4.4
Businessman	71	9.5
Others	442	59.2
The frequency of your current income*		
Every month	508	68.0
Every year	17	2.3
Others	222	29.7
The pharmacy chain is your first choice when having needs		
Yes	603	80.7
No	144	19.3
Usual spending on medicine per purchase?		
< 1.96\$	179	24.0
1.96\$–7.85\$	424	56.8
7.85\$–19.62\$	89	11.9
19.62\$–39.24\$	38	5.1
> 39.24\$	17	2.3
How many times do you buy per month?		
< 3	512	68.5
3–5	179	24.0
5–10	31	4.1
> 10	25	3.3

*"The frequency of your current income" is categorized based on the respondents' income payment schedule, including monthly payments (typically once at the end of each month or based on individual labor contracts) and yearly payments.

Table 2. Results of testing the reliability of the scales through Cronbach's alpha coefficients.

Survey variables	Variable-total correlation		CA coefficient
	Correlation coefficient-total	CA coefficient when eliminating variables	
Product quality			
PQ1. I feel the products meet my needs			0.909
	0.847	0.845	
PQ2. Products sold at pharmacy chains have a shelf life of more than 6 months			0.849
	0.843	0.849	
PQ3. Products at the pharmacy chain achieve treatment effectiveness			0.908
	0.772	0.908	
Brand name			
BN1. I trust the product quality through the pharmacy chain's brand			0.931
	0.868	0.892	
BN2. I can easily find information about the pharmacy through the chain's brand name			0.909
	0.851	0.909	
BN3. The pharmacy chain's brand makes me feel assured about the service quality			0.898
	0.870	0.898	
Price			
P1. I agree that the cheaper the price, the more customers like to shop at the store			0.989
	0.980	0.981	
P2. I often compare product prices between stores before making a purchase decision			0.991
	0.965	0.991	
P3. I appreciate stores that offer reasonable pricing policies			0.979
	0.983	0.979	
Facilities			
F1. My favorite pharmacy chain has a comfortable temperature, lighting, and open space			0.982
	0.967	0.969	
F2. My favorite pharmacy chain displays complete product pricing labels			0.980
	0.950	0.980	
F3. My favorite pharmacy chain is located on main roads and near markets			0.971
	0.964	0.971	
Convenience			
C1. My favorite pharmacy chain has a website and app for easy ordering and information lookup			0.983
	0.978	0.963	
C2. My favorite pharmacy chain offers home delivery service			0.999
	0.926	0.999	
C3. My favorite pharmacy chain has return and refund policies			0.960
	0.983	0.960	
Advertising and consumer promotion			
ACP1. Advertising policies influence my purchasing decisions			0.963
	0.940	0.932	
ACP2. I research and compare promotional programs among pharmacy chains			0.939
	0.929	0.939	
ACP3. Will you return to the pharmacy chain if there are more promotions?			0.966
	0.894	0.966	
Knowledge of employees			
KE1. I find that pharmacy chain staff are knowledgeable about medications			0.936
	0.860	0.913	
KE2. I feel satisfied when staff provide advice on pricing and product quality			0.894
	0.884	0.894	
KE3. I receive advice on medication usage, dosage, and side effects at the pharmacy chain			0.912
	0.861	0.912	
Selling skills			
SS1. I care about the staff's attitude when serving customers			0.998
	0.998	0.996	
SS2. Pharmacy chain staff can respond quickly and effectively to my needs			0.996
	0.998	0.996	
SS3. Staff's product consultation skills help me easily find suitable products			0.996
	0.997	0.996	
SS4. I will return to the pharmacy if the staff is friendly and enthusiastic.			0.997
	0.991	0.997	

Survey variables	Variable-total correlation		
	Correlation coefficient-total	CA coefficient when eliminating variables	CA coefficient
Loyalty			
L1. I will return because of the good product quality	0.933	0.969	0.975
L2. I will continue shopping because the pharmacy chain has a strong brand	0.929	0.970	
L3. I will return because the product prices are reasonable	0.932	0.969	
L4. I will return because the pharmacy has good facilities	0.940	0.969	
L5. I will return to shop because the pharmacy offers convenient services	0.940	0.969	
L6. I will return to the pharmacy chain if there are more promotions	0.903	0.972	
L7. I will return because the staff's consultation skills help me buy the right product	0.897	0.972	

Table 3. Descriptive statistics results and reliability (N = 747).

	Cronbach's Alpha	Mean	SD
PQ	0.909	4.0843	0.73034
BN	0.931	4.1156	0.75855
P	0.989	3.9670	0.74921
F	0.982	4.0995	0.68956
C	0.983	4.856	0.95695
ACP	0.963	4.2597	0.80238
KE	0.936	4.0437	0.90386
SS	0.998	4.1201	0.85279
L	0.975	4.1329	0.89426
Valid N(List wise)			

Table 4. The EFA result of the independent variables.

	Rotated Component Matrix ^a					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
SS1	0.863					
SS3	0.862					
SS4	0.858					
SS2	0.849					
KE1	0.822					
KE2	0.800					
KE3	0.791					
C3	0.752					
C1	0.750					
F1		0.912				
F2		0.907				
F3		0.903				
ACP2			0.931			
ACP1			0.928			
ACP3			0.915			
PQ3				0.845		
PQ2				0.824		
PQ1				0.806		
BN2					0.796	
BN1					0.724	
BN3					0.714	
P1						0.956
P3						0.946

Figure 2. Description of CFA results.

Table 5. The EFA result of the dependent variable.

Component Matrix ^a	
L2	0.962
L1	0.960
L3	0.957
L5	0.953
L7	0.937
L6	0.913

contributed to its corresponding construct. These results confirm that the questionnaire reliably measures the underlying theoretical constructs. The good fit indices suggest that the proposed factor structure is valid and appropriate for further analysis. This supports the unidirectionality of the measurement scales, as explained by Hu and Bentler (1999) in their work on cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis. This means that the constructs identified in the study (e.g., product quality, brand name) are well-defined and consistently measured, ensuring the reliability of the survey instrument.

SEM testing results

Fig. 3 shows that the model result appears to be a good fit for the actual data, with the following fit indices: GFI = 0.895, CFI = 0.981, TLI = 0.976 (all indices greater than 0.9), RMSEA = 0.057 (<0.08), PCLOSE = 0.002, and Chi-square/df = 3.401 (Hu and Bentler 1999).

Figure 3. SEM testing results.

Hypothesis testing results

The results depicted in Table 6 show the impact factors as follows: The analysis indicated that brand name (BN), price (P), facilities (F), convenience (C), knowledge of employees (KE), and selling skills (SS) all have positive and statistically significant effects on customer loyalty (L), with significance levels of $p < 0.05$.

Table 6. Description of hypothesis testing results.

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Hypothesis
L_ <--- PQ_	0.007	0.019	0.361	0.718	H1: Rejected
L_ <--- BN_	0.524	0.034	15.195	***	H2: Accepted
L_ <--- P_	0.045	0.014	3.182	0.001	H3: Accepted
L_ <--- F_	0.042	0.019	2.246	0.025	H4: Accepted
L_ <--- C_	0.116	0.015	7.904	***	H5: Accepted
L_ <--- ACP_	-0.013	0.015	-0.893	0.372	H6: Rejected
L_ <--- KE_	0.101	0.020	5.153	***	H7: Accepted
L_ <--- SS_	0.185	0.021	8.818	***	H8: Accepted

*Regression Weights: (Group number 1 – Default model) is the default label automatically generated by AMOS when only a single group is analyzed.

Discussion

General characteristics of research objects

Our research showed that a higher proportion of females (62.2%) in the survey population compared to males (37.8%). This finding is similar to Adat’s research on customer satisfaction in retail pharmacy chains in Durban (Adat 2013). The similarity can be attributed to the tendency of women to shop for cosmetics, drugs, and other medical supplies for their family. Most survey participants have an intermediate level (47.9%). This suggests that consumers generally possess basic knowledge about pharmaceuticals at pharmacy chains, but their understanding is not in-depth. The reason is that consumer knowledge is not scientifically proven due to differences in perspectives between consumers and drug manufacturers. In light of this, policymakers should raise social awareness by providing comprehensive information to consumers (Mohammadzadeh et al. 2017).

Factors affecting customers’ repurchase at pharmacy chains in Can Tho city

According to the survey results, we have identified several factors that, in line with existing literature (Mircheva and Pelev 2012), influence customers’ return to retail pharmacy chains, which are discussed in detail below.

Regarding product quality, most survey participants believe that the products sold at pharmacies have a shelf life of over six months and demonstrate good treatment effectiveness. However, a small portion of participants feel that the products at the pharmacy do not fully meet their needs. Various activities, including professional drug guidance and consulting services, have been implemented to provide buyers with comprehensive information. These efforts aim to enhance consumers’ understanding of the quality of products sold at pharmacy chains (Liu et al. 2021).

The brand of the pharmacy chain significantly influences customer attraction and retention. Nearly all survey participants trust the quality of products associated with the pharmacy chain’s brand. They find it easy to access information on the Internet, leading to a heightened sense of security when choosing a branded pharmacy. Customers have trust in the pharmacy chain’s brand because they believe that a product sold at a branded pharmacy chain has acceptable quality, which aligns with a study by Mohammadzadeh (Mohammadzadeh et al. 2017). Brand image is an asset that develops through the relationship between the pharmacy chain and its customers, so most customers will make purchasing choices based on product availability and brand image (Reinert and Murray 2017). This is demonstrated by successful examples such as Long Chau, Trung Son, and other well-known retail pharmacy chains in Can Tho City. Therefore, retail pharmacy chains should develop brand strategies to attract and retain a large customer base.

In terms of facilities and convenience, the pharmacy chain with airy space, display shelves with fully arranged price lists, a shopping website, a return policy, and the geographical location of the pharmacy chain are all elements that survey participants find highly appealing. The physical environment and all tangible aspects have a strongly positive influence on satisfaction and experience (Brandão and Ribeiro 2023). Promotional advertising policies are also regarded as a tangible feature since they can offer clients information about the type of service they expect and can play a vital role in enhancing customer satisfaction and generating long-term profits. Other tangible elements include consultation rooms, equipment, and promotional materials in a retail pharmacy chain (Adat 2013).

Price significantly impacts customer return in pharmacy chains, as it directly impacts their subconscious perceptions of product value. Survey respondents agree that lower prices increase return likelihood and compare prices between stores to prefer those with reasonable pricing. Therefore, pharmacy chain businesses should develop a pricing strategy that contributes to building the pharmacy chain's brand image, encouraging customers to make repeated purchases (Reinert and Murray 2017).

Most participants express satisfaction with pharmacy chain employees' knowledge and sales skills, particularly in providing advice on drug prices, quality, dosage, usage, and potential side effects, and show interest in their attitude and consulting skills. Hung found that, in situations where there was no opposition, people had a high belief in pharmacists' competence to prescribe antibiotics without a prescription and that they had the essential skills for patient consultation and administering antibiotics when needed (Hung et al. 2023). For that reason, this indicates that customers' trust in pharmacists has a highly positive influence on trust in the pharmacy chain.

Castaldo asserts that trust in community pharmacists is the primary driving force behind customer satisfaction. This trust not only directly influences satisfaction levels but also plays a crucial role, either directly or indirectly, in building trust in pharmacy chains (Castaldo et al. 2016). Therefore, pharmacy chains should enhance their staff's competencies, skills, and attitudes by carefully selecting and training employees. Mohammadzadeh also found that customer satisfaction increases when community pharmacists spend more time on consultation services (Mohammadzadeh et al. 2017).

When considering customer loyalty, the process of building loyalty is intricately tied to the quality of pharmacy services. The presence of a knowledgeable employee with a positive attitude plays a crucial role in enhancing customer satisfaction, making them more inclined to return for future purchases (Mircheva and Pelev 2012). Additionally, fulfilling customer needs by delivering excellent service quality is recognized as a key factor in fostering customer loyalty. This not only fosters customer satisfaction but also significantly contributes to shaping the image, reputation, and brand of pharmacy chains (Castaldo et al. 2016). Customer satisfaction is part of the brand

experience and can lead to loyalty and long-term relationships between the brand and its customers. These factors interact with each other, contributing to customer satisfaction with the pharmacy chain (Reinert and Murray 2017).

These factors positively influence customer returns to pharmacy chains in Can Tho City. It is imperative for pharmacy chains to develop comprehensive plans and policies. Neutralizing these factors will ensure the future success and development of pharmacy chains.

Conclusion

According to this survey, factors such as brand name, price, facilities, convenience, knowledge of employees, and selling skills were found to have statistically significant positive effects on customer loyalty. These findings emphasize the importance of improving both core product and service aspects (e.g., quality, pricing, and staff communication skills) as well as supporting factors (e.g., promotional activities and accessibility) to strengthen customer loyalty.

To gain loyal customers, pharmacies should strategically implement competitive strategies focused on delivering the optimum combination of service elements valued by clients, thereby establishing a unique competitive edge. Additionally, pharmacies should demonstrate adaptability and align with client expectations to achieve success and create a long-term customer network.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Can Tho university of medicine and pharmacy, Vietnam.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Vo Thi My Huong, Nguyen Phuc Hung: conceptualization, methodology, validation, resource, writing-review and editing; Nguyen Thi Tuyet Minh: writing – review and editing; Lam Quang Khai: investigation, resource; Tang Nghiep Minh: formal analysis, Luu Thai Quan, Ly Dang Khoa, Mai Thu Suong: investigation.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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